

Development and Performance Evaluation of Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology

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ABSTRACT

It is challenging to work on various tasks without a working table. In fashion industry, it is important to have a table where different workers will be able to perform their respective tasks. This study aimed to develop and evaluate the acceptability level of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table in terms of Kansei words such as multi-functionality, durability, and texture. To evaluate the ergonomic structure, the researchers, used the REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet. The respondents of the study were composed of ten (10) tailoring shop owners, ten (10) Fashion and Garments and Technology students, and ten (10)

professors. This study used descriptive and developmental methods of research. The researchers used four-point hedonic rating scale and REBA Assessment Employee Worksheet score as data-gathering instrument. The developed product was highly acceptable by the respondents. It also shows that it has a negligible risk level. Using Kruskal Wallis H Test, the researchers found out that there is a significant difference between the evaluations of the three group of respondents. Therefore, the developed product was acceptable and follow the ergonomic standard to prevent the musculoskeletal disorders. It is recommended to add another LED light tube and cabinet to the developed product.

Keywords: *Kansei words, REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet, Fashion and Garments and Technology Table, Ergonomic Standard*

INTRODUCTION

A table is an essential piece of furniture for any Fashion and Garments and Technology students, dressmakers, tailors, and fashion designers. They would need a table to work on various tasks. This task includes pattern drafting, fabric spreading, pattern manipulating, cutting fabric, transferring patterns and markings, and other processes in sewing garments. In the fashion industry, it is essential to have a table where different workers can perform their respective work. Every table that can see in the fashion industry has different functions and purposes, such as a cutting table for cutting fabrics and pattern paper, a spreading

table where they can quickly spread long and wide fabrics, and a drafting table where they can draft different patterns and pattern manipulation.

Mateo (2016) states that the table is mainly made to organize all sewing supplies so that dressmakers, tailors, and fashion designers have more breathing room for stitching. When sewing, having a table in the workspace makes it easier to work without feeling crowded and frees up room on the sewing machine. Additionally, the table must encourage excellent posture and be ergonomically sound to prevent work-related injuries and decrease pain and discomfort for workers, especially those who stand while working. (Prodigy Furniture, 2021).

A sewing table or tailor's table, in particular, can have specialist surfaces like a heat-resistant surface for ironing, a cut-resistant surface for cutting materials, and ergonomic features. Simple sewing tables can be as basic as a table or desk and are equipped with a level surface so that fabric can be laid out, measured, and cut, according to Peterson (2022).

It was beneficial for every tailor, dressmaker, and fashion designer in the Fashion and Garments and Technology students to have a multifunctional table in their workplace or working area. A multifunctional table will maximize available space where you do not need to move to another table since the table they use has unique features and additional functions that can make their work more accessible, more productive, and organize their workplace.

Palacios (2021) states that the sewing table needs to have a white laminate or a solid surface. Metal is frequently used to make sewing tables, but wood surface sewing tables are trendy because of their excellent durability. Sewing tables can have a light underneath, with good lighting, since it is vital to transfer the pattern in the fabric quickly. Lighting is also essential as it can help to see the difference between colors easily. It often comes with a built-in light that lets the dressmakers, tailors, and fashion designers sew in darkness, which means less eye strain and better results. Aside from lighting, it will help if the table has different features, such as an adjustable height feature, so they do not need to bend over when sewing.

However, the researchers observed that Fashion, Garments, and Technology lack tables, which is essential for students in this major in performing different tasks and laboratory activities. There are only two tables in the shop room, which needs improvement for the increasing number of students. It is also a plain table that is hard to use because it has a bulky surface that could be better when making a pattern. Accurate fabric cutting is also an issue because the fabric flits from the position, particularly when airy. The table is available for the students and cannot be pierced with pins when pinning the pattern paper and the fabric together, which causes it to move.

Similarly, with the lay-outing process of the pattern to the fabric, the students need help to spread the fabric quickly, which can cause uneven cuts. In addition, the students need help cutting the fabric, especially for mass production and advanced garments, since it is hard to lay flat lengthy, comprehensive fabrics on the table. Also, the table structure that the students are using could be more suitable for drawing patterns and ergonomically designed to maintain a good posture for the students while engaged in laboratory

activities. Aside from it, the table needs to be ergonomically correct, and the height of the table needs to be more suitable and leveled to the height of the students.

With this information, the researchers developed and evaluated an innovative Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table that addressed the stated research gap of the Fashion and Garments and Technology students, tailors or dressmakers, and fashion designers. A Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table was made into different types of metal to secure its durability. This table has multiple features or functions essential for tailors or dressmakers, fashion designers, and Fashion and Garment Technology students. It has a built-in spreader to spread the fabric quickly and, at the same time, can be a pinning table since the half measurement of the table has a hole on the right side and left side. It has a pin cushion that is made of sand under the table that is aligned to the hole to easily pierce the fabric and the pattern paper with the use of a pin and can remove the pins after the pinning process to secure their safety while using the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table.

Additionally, it can be used as a drafting table and cutting table in laboratory activities, such as cutting stencil designs for silk screen printing. The surface of the top table was made into glass, and LED tube lights were installed under the top and bottom sides so that the light would reflect at the top to smoothly transfer the markings and trace the pattern to the fabric. The Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table has an adjustable height so that the height of the table will become suitable for the different heights of the students so that they do not bend too much while working and can easily change their working position. This study aimed to help the students in their laboratory activities quickly. Also, they can utilize and become familiarized with the different tools and equipment the fashion industry uses in their work and production process. Hence, this proposed study to develop and evaluate the multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table.

Objectives

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the acceptability of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table in terms of Kansei word (Zhafira, et.al, 2018) such multi-functionality, durability and texture, evaluate the ergonomic structure of the developed product using the REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet in terms of neck position, trunk position, leg position, upper arm position, lower arm position and wrist position, determine the significance differences on the evaluations of the three groups of respondents, estimate the cost of production and gather comments and suggestions to improve the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table.

METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive and developmental methods of research. A total of 30 (tailoring shop owners, Fashion and Garments and Technology students and professors related to Fashion and Garments and Technology) were chosen as the respondents of the study using purposive sampling technique. An adapted evaluation questionnaire and adapted REBA Employee Assessment worksheet was used to collect data and evaluate the acceptability of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table in

terms of Kansei word (Zhafira, et.al, 2018) such multi-functionality, durability and texture and its ergonomic structure using the REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet in terms of neck position, trunk position, leg position, upper arm position, lower arm position and wrist position. Weighted mean and Kruskal Wallis H-Test were used as statistical tools for analyzing and interpreting the data gathered in this study.

Materials and Procedure

Development of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table

A. Planning and Designing

- The Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table was planned through sketching and transferring it to AutoCAD application.

B. Gathering of Materials

- Materials
 - ✓ Round bar
 - ✓ Aluminum tubular
 - ✓ Angle bar
 - ✓ Welding rod
 - ✓ Glass
 - ✓ Led fluorescent
 - ✓ Round cable
 - ✓ Plug
 - ✓ Fabric
 - ✓ Sealant
 - ✓ Spray paint
 - ✓ Electrical tape
 - ✓ Caster wheel with lock
 - ✓ Trolley wheel with lock
 - ✓ Insolation foam
 - ✓ Stick glue
 - ✓ Grinding wheel disc
 - ✓ Clear hook
 - ✓ Cutting disc

C. Assembling

C1. For Making a Drafting, Cutting and Pinning Glass Table

- Planning and designing the concept in developing the Multifunctional fashion and Garments and Technology Table.
- Purchasing and preparing all the needed materials in developing a Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table.
- Measuring and cutting the metals such as three 243.84 cm and two 96.52 cm' tubular steel and angle bar for the width and length of the table frame, two 101.6 cm and two 91.44 cm' tubular steel for table leg, and 96.52 cm x 243.84 cm glass for the top table.
- Welding the tubular steel together for the framing.
- Resizing the tubular steel for adjustment of the leg.
- Attaching wheels on the legs of the table.
- Drilling holes in the leg of the table.
- Welding the legs of the table to the aluminum steel frame of the table.
- Welding a support to the legs and frame of the table.
- Welding and attaching the angle bar inside the aluminum steel frame of the table.
- Cutting the aluminum steel in half for the roller wheel guide of the spreader.
- Welding the two-half aluminum steel in the top and bottom side of the frame of the table.

- Attaching pin cushion under the table which is aligned with the hole of the top table.
- Drilling a hole on the table that will serve as a pin hole.
- Attaching the glass top table on the frame of the table using sealant.
- Installing LED tube lights under the top and bottom part of the table.

C2. For Developing Manual Fabric Spreader

- Cutting metals such as two 38.1 cm, two 7.62 cm, and two 24.4 cm' tubular steel and 101.6 cm and 96.52 cm round bar.
- Welding together the 38.1 cm, 7.62 cm and 25.40 cm' tubular steel to make a two frame for the left side and right side of the manual fabric spreader.
- Connecting the right and left side of the spreader using the 96.52 cm round bar by welding it together.
- Attaching a hook 12.7 cm downward from the front top of the frame of the manual fabric spreader.
- Attaching the wheels on the four sides of the frame of the manual fabric spreader.
- Putting the 101.6 cm round bar at the hook.

C3. For Developing the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table

- Applying paint on the developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table.
- Attaching the built- in manual fabric spreader in the left side of the table.
- Final touching, checking and testing of the developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table.
- Evaluating the multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table.

Figure 1. **Developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table**

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Evaluation of Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table in Terms of Kansei Words; Multi-functionality, Durability and Texture

The evaluation results show that the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table is “*Highly Acceptable*” for the three groups of respondents that evaluated the product in terms of multi-functionality, durability, and texture. Specifically, the Fashion and Garments and Technology students have the highest average mean rating of 3.98 in all the attributes of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table of the three groups of respondents. This finding implied that the students benefit the most from the developed product. The Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table will inspire the student to work effectively and efficiently because they have a multifunctional table that they can use and will help them to perform multi-tasking in their laboratory activities efficiently. Using the developed product in their courses related to pattern drafting, transferring marks on the fabric, fabric cutting, and material spreading will benefit them. They can practice using different tools and equipment that the industry use. Professors related to Fashion, Garments, and Technology have an average mean rating of 3.81, while the tailoring shop owner has an average mean rating of 3.76 which was the lowest.

It is supported by the article of Jeani Young, Ph.D. (2020) of Indiana University, that when the students review instructional materials, they examine how fascinating, approachable, and engaging it is. It is not about whether materials are “entertaining” but whether they may arouse curiosity and inspire more profound thought about the matter. In addition, according to study of Hepler et al. (2022), which states that educators ensure that the materials they utilize support learning and serve that purpose rather than distracting pupils from their studies. When educators review and choose conventional materials to teach their students, the most crucial factor they should consider in an instructional material like multifunctional furniture, tools, and equipment is the overall functions of the product that can help the students meet a learning standard.

Table 1. *Respondents Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table*

Respondents	Multi-Functionality		Durability		Texture		General Average	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
Tailoring Shop Owner	3.76	HA	3.86	HA	3.66	HA	3.76	HA
Fashion and Garments and Technology Students	3.98	HA	3.98	HA	3.98	HA	3.98	HA
Professors Related to Fashion and	3.74	HA	3.94	HA	3.76	HA	3.81	HA

Garments and Technology								
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Evaluation of the Ergonomic Structure of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table using Rapid Entire Body Assessment in terms Neck Position, Trunk Position, Leg Position, Upper Arm Position, Lower Arm Position and Wrist Position

The results of the evaluation of the three groups of respondents in the ergonomic structure of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table using REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet shows that regarding the neck position, the overall mean based on the evaluation of the three groups of respondents was 1.5, and the risk level was "Negligible." Regarding trunk position, the general standard was 1.8, which had a "Negligible" risk level based on the respondent's evaluation.

Based on the review of the three groups of respondents, there is a 1.2 overall mean in terms of the leg position with a risk level of "Negligible" based on the review of the three groups of respondents. The general means the three groups of respondents gave in terms of the lower arm and upper arm position was 1.2, and the risk level was "Negligible." In terms of wrist position, the overall mean was 1.3, with a "Negligible" risk level.

These findings implied that the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table was ergonomically correct and followed the standard height of a working table which can help to prevent musculoskeletal disorders while working. The adjustable height features of the multifunctional table were suitable for the users to have a good posture and be comfortable while doing different tasks and adjust according to their height which makes the table's structure ergonomically correct.

These findings are parallel to the study of Salameh and Abdallah (2020) entitled "Design and Analysis of an Ergonomic- Automated Adjustable Drafting Table," students, teachers, and tailors experience discomfort, back pain, and neck pain as a result of the tables' fixed dimensions, which are incompatible with the dimensions of their bodies. A mechanical design of power screws and an electrical circuit created an automated drafting table with three flexible joints. Students much appreciate the proposed method over the fixed one now in use since it has an adjustable height, width, and desktop inclination with an automatic mechanism.

Table 2. Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents in the Ergonomic Structure of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table using Rapid Entire Body Assessment in terms Neck Position, Trunk Position, Leg Position, Upper Arm Position, Lower Arm Position and Wrist Position

Respondents	Neck Position		Trunk Position		Leg Position		Upper Arm Position		Lower Arm Position		Wrist Position		Ave. Mean	R L
	W M	R L	W M	RL	W M	RL	W M	RL	W M	RL	W M	R L		
Tailoring Shop Owner	1.5	N	2	L	1.2	N	1.2	N	1.4	N	1.1	N	1.4	N
Fashion and Garments and Technology Students	1.6	N	2	L	1.2	N	1.4	N	1.1	N	1.1	N	1.4	N
Professors Related to Fashion and Garments and Technology	1.3	N	1.5	N	1.2	N	1	N	1	N	1.2	N	1.2	N
Overall Mean	1.5	N	1.8	N	1.2	N	1.2	N	1.2	N	1.1	N	1.3	N

As shown in the table below, the computed REBA Score based on evaluating the three groups of respondents in the ergonomic structure of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table. This shows that the risk level of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table was “*LOW*,” and the action was “*May be Necessary*,” based on the evaluation of the three groups of respondents while using the product with an overall of 2.5. The tailoring shop owner rated Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table with the highest score of 2.7 with a description of Low-risk level. These findings implied that the tailoring shop owner used to work traditionally in the industry, where some of their tables were not ergonomically correct for their working posture. The tailors typically spend long hours standing while doing their tasks, such as pattern drafting, fabric cutting, transferring marks and lines on the fabric, and fabric spreading. While using the Multifunctional Table, they might adjust the height of the table not suitable to the size of the worker, which results in a bad posture and discomfort while using the table.

According to the study by Singh (2019) entitled “Postural Analysis of the Tailors of Allahabad District,” the results also showed that all of the chosen tailors who performed the cutting and drafting of clothing using the traditional method of tailoring operations experienced pain in their necks, shoulders,

joints, and lumber region. The Fashion and Garments and Technology students gave 2.6, and the professors related to Fashion and Garments and Technology gave 2.3.

Table 3. *Respondents REBA Score of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table*

Respondents	REBA Score	Risk Level	Action
Tailoring Shop Owner	2.7	Low	May be Necessary
Fashion and Garments and Technology Students	2.6	Low	May be Necessary
Professors Related to Fashion and Garments and Technology	2.3	Low	May be Necessary
Overall Mean	2.5	Low	May be Necessary

Significant Differences Among the Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents in the Developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table

The table below shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents using the Kruskal Wallis Test. The Kruskal Wallis Test indicates a significant difference in the assessment among the three groups of respondents with .003 significant, which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between the professor's perception related to Fashion and Garments and Technology, and the Fashion and Garments and Technology students affect the variable, which is the multi- functionality, durability, and texture.

According to the article from the University of Michigan entitled "Why Are Teacher and Student Perceptions Different?" that the perception of teachers and students when evaluating a garment table can be different due to a variety of factors. According to research conducted by the University of Michigan, teachers may have different expectations for students than students have for themselves. Teachers may also be more likely to focus on the technical aspects of the garment table, such as its construction and design, while students may be more focused on its aesthetic appeal.

Additionally, teachers may have more experience with garment tables and thus be able to identify flaws or areas for improvement that students may need to recognize. Finally, teachers may also have different standards for grading a garment table than students do.

Table 4. *Significant Differences Among the Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Overall Acceptability of the Developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table*

Hypothesis Test Summary				
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of OVERALL is the same across categories of RESPONDENTS.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.003	Reject the null hypothesis.
Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.				

Sample1-Sample2	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.	Adj.Sig.
TEACHERS-TAILORS	2.400	3.818	.629	.530	1.000
TEACHERS-STUDENTS	12.450	3.818	3.261	.001	.007
TAILORS-STUDENTS	10.050	3.818	2.632	.008	.051

Each row tests the null hypothesis that the Sample 1 and Sample 2 distributions are the same.
 Asymptotic significances (2-sided tests) are displayed. The significance level is .05.

Computed Cost of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table

The table below presented the materials and tools, quantity used, unit price, and the total cost of the developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table. It can be noted that the materials used by the researchers in developing Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table cost the total amount of **₱14, 104.00**.

Table 5. *Computed Cost of Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table*

Materials	Measurement	Quantity	Unit Price	Total Price
Round bar	10 mm (20 feet)	1 pc	₱ 215.00	₱ 215.00
Aluminum tubular	1 inch x 1 inch (20 feet)	2 pcs	₱ 610.00	₱ 1,220.00
Aluminum tubular	1 inch x 1 inch (20 feet)	1 pc	₱ 420.00	₱ 420.00
Angle bar	1/8 x 1 inch (20 feet)	2 pcs	₱ 300.00	₱ 600.00
Welding rod		1 kl	₱ 96.00	₱ 96.00

Glass		1 pc	₱ 3,400.00	₱ 3,400.00
Led fluorescent		2 pcs	₱ 200.00	₱ 400.00
Round cable	4 meters	1 pc	₱ 23.00	₱ 92.00
Plug		1 pc	₱ 20.00	₱ 20.00
Electrical tape		1 pc	₱ 40.00	₱ 40.00
Sealant		2 pcs	₱ 200.00	₱ 400.00
Spray paint		4 pcs	₱ 120.00	₱ 480.00
Caster wheel with lock	1 inch	4 pcs	₱ 29.00	₱ 116.00
Trolley wheel with lock	2 inches	4 pcs	₱ 51.00	₱ 204.00
Fabric	½ yard	1 pc	₱ 20.00	₱ 20.00
Insulation foam	2 yards	1 pc	₱ 54.00	₱ 108.00
Stick glue		30 pcs	₱ 4.00	₱ 120.00
Grinding wheel disc		3 pcs	₱ 16.00	₱ 48.00
Masking tape		2 pcs	₱ 30.00	₱ 60.00
Clear hook		2 pcs	₱ 40.00	₱ 40.00
Drill bit	10 mm	1 pc	₱ 66.00	₱ 66.00
Cutting disc		3 pcs	₱ 13.00	₱ 39.00
Transportation				₱ 2,000.00
Labor				₱ 4,000.00
			Total	₱ 14,104.00

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the aforementioned findings, it can be concluded that the developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table is deemed highly acceptable based on the rating from the tailoring shop owner, Fashion and Garments and Technology students, and professors related to Fashion and Garments and Technology in terms of Kansei Word (2018), which are multi-functionality, durability and texture. For the ergonomic structure of the Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology was negligible regarding neck position, trunk position, leg position, upper arm position, lower arm position, and wrist position using the REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet. And the overall risk level while using the product, according to the groups of respondents, was low, with the action may be necessary.

There is a significant difference between the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability level of the developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. The total cost of production of the developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table appeared to be worth ₱ 14 104.00. The develop Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table could be improved by following the suggestions and comments of the respondents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study the following recommendations were offered: further detailed study should be conducted about the research product and study using Rapid Entire Body Assessment Worksheet, in order to assess in detail, the ergonomic design and risk factor and risk level of the developed Multifunctional Fashion and Garments and Technology Table. The respondents recommended to installed one LED tube lights in the center under the table so that it will produce brighter light. The Fashion and Garments and Technology students recommended to have a put a measurement or measuring scale on the side of table that was expressed in inch or centimeter to easily measure the needed fabric. Attach a store area under the table where they can store different tools, materials and other equipment in cutting, sewing, and pattern drafting and to store fabrics.

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